

THE EFFECTS OF MULTIPLE SENSES ON THE VOCABULARY SKILLS OF CHILDREN WITH DYSLEXIA IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

Ngong, Aghi Aaron (Ph.D)

IBE BELLO

aghi_abc@yahoo.com

Abstract

Vocabulary skills can greatly increase the reading ability of children with dyslexia. This paper investigates the use of multiple senses in teaching vocabulary skills and hence the reading skills of children with dyslexia in some selected elementary schools in Mezam Division, North West of Cameroon. A quasi-experimental approach used 2 groups of pre/post-test research designs that measured pupils' performances before and after a month of intense instruction. 24 class five children with dyslexia from Educare Bilingual Nursery and Primary School and All Saints Bilingual Nursery and Primary School, Bayelle were qualified through a study of their class records and their performance in reading high-frequency words. Pupils were randomly selected using a lottery method for the experimental and Control groups. The Children's preferred learning styles were employed in teaching them in the experimental group, using a master plan of activities, meanwhile, their regular teachers taught the same content to the control groups for a month. Using the SPSS version 25, descriptive and inferential tools were employed to verify the hypotheses. Interestingly the Experimental group performed better than the control group with a large effect size. Thus, the use of multiple senses in the teaching-learning arena greatly facilitates learning for all school children especially those with dyslexia.

Keywords: Multiple senses; Dyslexia; Reading ability; Vocabulary skills

Introduction

When Troeva (2016:366) postulates that reading is not enshrined in our genome, the Centre for Education Statistics and Evaluation (2017: 2) reaffirms this by attesting that at the commencement of formal education, children's literacy skills are challenged because reading is not innate as compared to speech. The reading process is cumbersome because learners need to focus on print primarily to decipher words, implying that they must possess good vision or use the tactile senses on their fingers for those who are visually challenged. They must have their eyeballs move flexibly, forward and backward, up and down, on the letters of the alphabet and words and vice versa, without neglecting to judge appropriate spaces within letters and in words.

The ability to transform letters of the English alphabet (graphemes) into sounds (phonemes) is a prerequisite and the effort to decipher the onset and rimes in words is also crucial. They must be able to blend, delete, add, or combine letter sounds to form true and pseudowords. In the same light picking the various syllables in words-monosyllables, bi-syllables, etc. are important to read long and short words. The idea that some words will not always be read as their letter combinations show, is vital because they normally do not follow the spelling rules taught. This is exemplified in words such as psyche, physics, pneumonia, etc. These words are referred to as "sight words". So, emergent readers and especially those with dyslexia will need at some point to memorize the spellings of some words.

Reading is a complex foundational cognitive skill that requires word decoding, spelling, reading comprehension and speech. The importance of reading can't be overemphasized for it trains one's mind and broadens one's outlook, exposes readers to their cultures, and places; builds esteem, and even improves one's vocabulary. Yet for children with dyslexia, it is a daunting task.

For children without dyslexia it is appreciable to teach vocabulary using explanations, demonstrations, translations, incidental approaches or by inferring word meanings from the text. A lexically classroom-built environment will enhance a multi-sensory teaching approach to vocabulary. This will help learners to build their receptive and expressive knowledge of words, which is crucial for reading.

Use of Multiple Senses for Instruction

A multi-sensory approach intentionally involves more than one learner's senses during instruction; that is seeing (Visual), hearing (Auditory), touching (tactile) and manipulating (Kinesthetic). Aborigines of multi-sensory instruction include Montessori (1912), who used this style to teach exceptional children by exposing many objects and toys for them to play with. When teaching children with dyslexia, it is preferable to vary methods, and value their learning styles or preferred styles, especially their tactile and kinesthetic senses. These senses focus the learner's attention to the learning content as information is wholly channeled to the brain. In this study, the researcher provided opportunities for all the learners to see, hear, discuss, touch, and manipulate at once during vocabulary instruction using a master plan of activities.

African scholars like Aja et al (2017) emphasize the importance and place of multiple senses during instruction and demonstrate how they motivate both teachers and learners in knowledge acquisition. Teaching vocabulary items to learners with dyslexia therefore will be good to bring real objects, toys, pictures, drawings, sketches, videos, computers, overhead projectors, etc to the classrooms. Accordingly, children will handle, smell, feel, (possibly taste) manipulate or play with them. All the stimuli channeled to the brain improve learning, stimulate not only the sensory registers but the long-term memories, and also facilitate recall.

Conceptualising Dyslexia and its Impact on Learners

According to the International Dyslexia Association, (2017: 3). *Dyslexia is a specific learning disability that is neurological in origin. It is characterized by difficulties with accurate and/or fluent word recognition and by poor spelling and decoding abilities. These difficulties typically result from a deficit in the phonological component of language that is often unexpected in relation to other cognitive abilities and the provision of effective classroom instruction. Secondary consequences may include problems in reading comprehension and reduced reading experience that can impede the growth of vocabulary and background knowledge.*

According to Dyslexia Friendly Policy (nd) children with dyslexia look intelligent but have literacy challenges. Nursery school children may exhibit difficulties with saying rhymes, while post-nursery learners exhibit difficulty in differentiating 'left' from 'right'; and have poor receptive and expressive language skills; are forgetful and with difficulty committing to memory of learned material; lack confidence in reading; omit or repeat lines- a loss of place value in the text; muddle similar looking words e.g.: 'no' with 'on', 'for' with 'off', 'was' with 'saw.'; exhibit challenges with pronouncing many syllable words; and comprehension challenges. Vocabulary instruction using a multi-sensory approach could greatly improve their reading skills. Linguists (NICHD, 2000) suggest five competencies necessary for teaching young children reading especially through their vocabulary skills.

Vocabulary Skills

Vocabulary refers to all the words used in a language as a particular language. It is the knowledge of word meanings and pronunciations (lexicon). It is therefore the building blocks of every language. Vocabulary knowledge is exhibited when pupils listen, speak, read and write correctly. Two key vocabulary types are receptive and expressive vocabulary. Receptive vocabulary constitutes meanings made when children hear someone speak or read texts with understanding. Meanwhile, expressive vocabulary is considered the child's property when he or she

speaks out correctly or writes correctly. That is a hallmark of one's reading capacity. Word recognition vocabulary is necessary because it leads to comprehension with time and also increases reading fluency and speed.

Elwer, (2014:23) posits that children's vocabulary breadth be widened by exposing children to much content thereby increasing their mental lexicon and vocabulary depth by refining word meanings known as semantic representation in their lexicon. Individual vocabulary there depends on the number of new words received in one's mental lexicon. According to Elwer (2014:23) increasing vocabulary breadth is promoting decoding skills. Vocabulary depth increases comprehension skills in both oral and written forms. Helping children to increase their oral language skills is going to improve their reading proficiency skills too (Shore & Sabatini 2009:17).

The NSW Centre for Effective Learning (2014:3) upholds that possessing good vocabulary skills entails possessing reading comprehension skills. So then, word meanings aid comprehension; develop phonemic awareness, decoding and reading fluency. Neuman and Wright (2014:5) support this view by stating that emergent learners' high vocabulary content directly improves their reading abilities.

The NSW Centre for Effective Learning (2014:4) qualifies that nursery school children who possess good vocabulary content have good comprehension skills. This helps them to read more and to study new words on their own. By extension, they perform better in other school subjects. Classroom teachers should do everything within their reach to increase the vocabulary content of children with dyslexia as this is going to accelerate holistic growth in diverse subject areas. Poor vocabulary content correlates to difficulties in word identification, hesitant speech, reluctance in classroom participation, conversation with peers, incorrect responses, and general retardation in ascending the academic rungs (Wise, Sevcik, Morris, Lovett, & Wolf, 2007:11). In contrast, good vocabulary knowledge is correlated with good reading achievement, comprehension and learners grow from "learning to read" to "reading to learn" (Hairrell, Rupley, & Simmons, 2011:14). Good oral vocabulary skills, aid word identification and reading skills.

The NSW Centre for Effective Learning (2014:4) advises that pre-kindergartens vocabulary could be developed by their parents as they engage them in exciting conversations as they play, travel, watch television, give them exciting stories to read for leisure, as they return from the farm, market, church, mosque etc or wherever contexts that some new words are used quite often. Probe children to give their views on current events and happenings; directly teaching meanings of words, contextual teaching of word meanings, helping learners to figure out word meanings from texts and an uncommon practice is for children to refer word meanings from dictionaries and other reference books. Shanahan (2005:27) supports direct teaching of vocabulary items by opening that, learners repeat new words displayed on word walls and contextual learning.

When teachers display real items, take children to places to observe, manipulate, and play with items, allowing them to restate with their own words, etc, this could aid children with dyslexia in developing their vocabulary skills and aid their reading and comprehension skills. With all these issues raised, teachers can use vocabulary instruction to mitigate the effects of dyslexia.

Statement of the Problem

Globalisation is bringing the whole world into a small village. The reading skill is key, to have everyone fit into this global context. However, children with dyslexia are challenged because their reading, writing, spelling, and speaking skills are not developing as other developmental markers. Classroom teachers are not sufficiently equipped with specific skills to teach reading to children with dyslexia. They are compelled to use a one-size-fit-all approach of the traditional instructional approach where learners are forced to sit silently and attentively, fold their arms, listen, understand and may ask questions just at the end, meanwhile, the teacher is the one who is most active,

doing the talking and explanations without much consideration to know if the learners are assimilating the content. This makes the classrooms dormant, boring and unattractive to all.

However, most children with dyslexia are active, full of energy and can't be rendered docile just by the teacher's instructions. They need to see, touch, handle, taste, and manipulate objects, as their multiple senses are aroused and entail a greater brain involvement and absorption of content, thereby increasing learning outcomes. It is for this reason that the study intends to investigate how effective the multiple senses affect teaching reading to pupils with dyslexia by improving their vocabulary skills?"

Specific Objective: To assess the effects of the multiple senses in building vocabulary skills of primary school children with dyslexia.

Specific Research Questions: To what extent does the use of multiple senses affect the growth of vocabulary competencies of children with dyslexia?

Specific Hypotheses

H01: There is no significant difference in the vocabulary competencies of children with dyslexia, taught using their multiple senses, in comparison to those not taught not using their multiple senses.

Ha1: There is a significant difference in the vocabulary competencies of children with dyslexia, taught using their multiple senses, in comparison to those not taught not using the multiple senses.

Research Methodology

Research Design, Sample and Sampling Techniques

The quasi-experimental research design was utilized as multiple visits to schools led to discussions with both administrative authorities and classroom teachers to get clues about children with reading challenges. Both class records and individual reading performances were considered clues for confirming children with dyslexia. A test comprising High-frequency words was issued and learners' performances were captured. 24 pupils were randomly chosen and placed into 2 groups i.e. 12 in the Control and 12 in the Experimental group. Intensive teaching using the multiple senses was done for the experimental group for a month, using a master plan of activities developed by the researcher while the classroom teachers used the same content in teaching the control group within the same period. These children were selected from the All Saints Bilingual Primary and Nursery School Bayelle Nkwen and Educare Bilingual Nursery and Primary School, all in Bamenda 111 Sub Division using the lottery method through the multi-stage sampling approach.

Method of data processing and analysis

The SPSS version 25 utilized the descriptive analysis for calculations of means and standard deviations to obtain performances of children before and after interventions for both the control and experimental groups. Inferential statistics for one sample t-test, the independent t-test, and Cohen *d*, were used to test effect size.

The Research question sought to find out how the use of multiple senses in teaching Vocabulary skills, influences the reading competencies of children with dyslexia.

Table 1: Descriptive Results of Pre-and Post-test Vocabulary Skills Scores for Control and Experimental Groups

	Group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max
Pre-test	Control	12	11.66	2.708	5.00	14.00
	Experimental	12	8.08	4.48	.00	15.00
Post-test	Control	12	12.00	3.78	2.00	15.00
	Experimental	12	15.58	4.378	5.00	20.00

Source: Computed by Author, 2019

Table 1 shows the results obtained for Vocabulary skills at pre/test and post/test for the control and experimental groups. For the control and experimental groups, their scores were 11.66/20 and 8.08/20 at pre/test with a standard deviation value of 2.70 and 4.48 respectively. The control group’s minimum score was 5/20 and 14/20 maximum. The experimental group had a minimum of 00/20 and a maximum of 15/20.

In the post-test, both groups experienced increases in mean scores (12/20 and 15.58/20 respectively) with average mean increases of 0.3 and 7.5 for the control and experimental groups respectively, indicating that the use of the multiple senses was profitable. For the control group, the minimum score was 2 and the maximum was 15. For the Experimental group, the minimum was 5.00 and the maximum was 20/20, indicating that the use of multiple senses is effective in the acquisition of vocabulary skills of children with dyslexia.

In verifying the research hypothesis, **Ho1** stated that there is no significant difference in vocabulary skills of children with dyslexia, taught using the multiple senses, as compared to those taught not using them.

Table 2: One-Sample t-test of Pretest and Posttest for Vocabulary Skills of the Experimental Group

Group	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	df	T	Sig	Cohen <i>d</i>
Pre-test	12	11.66	2.70	3.91	22	2.63	.015	1.075
Post-test	12	15.58	4.37					

Source: Computed by Author, 2019

Table 2 showed that at the pretest the pupils had a mean score of 11.66 (SD = 2.70), and at the posttest they had a mean of 15.58 (SD = 4.37), giving a mean increase of 3.91, conclusive that multiple senses contributed in developing their vocabulary. Subjecting these values to a one-sample t-test, a t-value of 2.63 was obtained at 22 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.015 ($P < 0.05$). Hence the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative retained. For the effect size, Cohen’s *d* value was 1.07, indicating a large and significant effect size. The Children’s reading skills therefore improved by 33.57%.

Table 3: Independent Sample t-test of the Experimental group and control group to examine if the use of multiple senses improved performances as compared to those taught without using them.

Group	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	df	T	Sig
Experimental Group	12	15.58	4.37	1.25	22	0.960	0.49
Control Group	12	14.33	4.499				

From Table 3 the experimental group had a mean score of 15.58 (SD = 4.37), and those in the control group had a mean of 14.33 (SD = 4.49), showing a mean difference of 1.25, which indicates that the use of multiple senses improved the vocabulary skills. These results show that after intervention children with dyslexia taught using their multiple senses performed better and so the results obtained at $t(22) = .96, p = 0.49$. The null hypothesis was then rejected and the study concluded that children with dyslexia, taught using their multiple senses, performed better in vocabulary skills than their counterparts not taught using their multiple senses.

Discussion and Conclusion

At post/test, both groups recorded increases in mean scores but more for the experimental group, implying that the intervention with the multiple senses registered a substantial increment in vocabulary scores among children with dyslexia. This was confirmed by Elwer (2014:23) who averred that a large vocabulary promotes decoding but vocabulary depth is an indication of strong reading comprehension competencies. These results were also supported by the research done by the National Reading Panel of the National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (NICHD, 2000), which identified vocabulary instruction as an essential skill that students need, to improve reading performance.

It was also found that at the post-test, children with dyslexia were subjected to a reading comprehension exercise in which all aspects of vocabulary skills were examined. Greater improvements were recorded in the experimental group over the control group. Impressively, learners were able to read, identify, match, and write down terms as required. To complement this, the NSW Centre for Effective Learning (2014:3) states that good vocabulary skills are contributors to comprehension: teaching learners word meanings aids understanding, aids the development of phonemic awareness, and aids both concrete decoding of words and reading fluency.

In the same line of thought, the Centre for the Improvement of Early Reading Achievement (2001), posits that teaching vocabulary using the multiple senses for children with dyslexia is supported because of the use of all of their senses as this aids storage and retrieval of vocabulary items. The multi-sensory learning approach activates all the senses in teaching reading. So, teachers must ensure that they bring instructional materials into their classrooms to keep the pupils actively engaged in observing, emitting hypotheses, exchanging viewpoints, and playing with materials during instruction. This conveys information across to the brain, and aids in assimilation and retrieval (Birsh, 2001).

References

Aja, S. N. et. al (2017). Using Multi-Sensory Instruction in Managing Classrooms for Effective Teaching and Learning. *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, 12, (24) 15112-15118.

Birsh, J. R. (2001). *Multisensory instruction*. Newsletter Archive. Retrieved on 19 March 2018 from <http://www.brookespublishing.com/email/archive/february01/february01ED1.htm>

- Centre for Education Statistics and Evaluation (2017). *Effective Reading Instruction in the Early Years of School*. Sydney. Retrieved on 30th October 2018 from www.cese.nsw.gov.au, cese@det.nsw.edu.au.
- Collier, L. (2007). *Effective vocabulary instruction*. The Council Chronicle. Retrieved on March 19, 2018 from <http://www.ncte.org/print.asp?id=126806&node=1312>.
- Dalecki, C. G. (2007). *Improving Letter and Word Recognition Using a Multisensory Approach*. Education and Human Development Master's Theses. 282. The College at Brockport.
- Ellis, A. and Young, A. (1988). *Human Cognitive Neuropsychology*. London: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Ellis, E. and Farmer, T. (2005). *Multisensory vocabulary instruction: Guidelines and activities*. Reading rockets. Retrieved March 18, 2018 from <http://www.readingrockets.org/article/286?theme=print>.
- Elwér, A. (2014). Early Predictors of Reading Comprehension Difficulties. *Linköping Studies in Behavioural Science*, 1(1), 186.
- Gustafson, S. (2000). *Varieties of reading disability Phonological and orthographic word decoding deficits and implications for interventions*. Helsinki, Sweden: The Swedish Institute for Disability Research.
- Hairrell, A., Rupley, W. and Simmons, D. (2011). The state of vocabulary research. *Literacy Research and Instruction*, 50(4), 253 - 271.
- International Dyslexia Association (2014). *What Every Family Should Know*. Retrieved October 30, 2018, from IDA www.interdys.org.
- Nash, M. and Donaldson, M. (2005). Word Learning in Children with Vocabulary Deficits. *Journal of Speech, Language and Hearing Research*, 48,439-458.
- National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (NICHD) (2000). *Report of the National Reading Panel: Reports of the subgroups. Teaching children to read: An evidence-based assessment of the scientific research literature on reading and its implications for reading instruction* (NIH Pub No. 00-4754). Washington, DC: Government Printing Office.
- Neuman, S. B. and Wright, T. S. (2014). The Magic Words: Teaching Vocabulary in the Early Childhood Classrooms. *American Educator*, Retrieved on the 30th of October 2018 from www.americaneducator.edu.
- NSW Centre for Effective Reading (2014). Working with students with language impairment: Vocabulary. *Education and Communities teacher resources*, (1).
- Troeva, B. (2016). The process of Reading and the Teaching of Reading Skills to Pupils with Dyslexia, *Pedagogy: Bulgarian Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 38, (3) 366-386.